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SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING OF OCEAN FRONTS AND CURRENTS OFF MID-NORWAY

**A study for
A/S Norske Shell
Under
Norwegian Deepwater Programme
Metocean Project**

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Executive summary

The background for this project is the requirements from the oil industry to obtain more knowledge about currents and eddies for the deepwater exploration west of Mid-Norway. The study is part of the Metocean Project of the Norwegian Deep Water Programme coordinated by Norske Shell.

In this study more than 60 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) scenes from the ERS-2 satellite, each covering 100 by 100 km, were investigated for low wind conditions allowing observation of current patterns and fronts. Location, scale and rotation of eddies was determined from the SAR images. The eddy circulation from SAR images was compared with in situ current measurements from arrays of moorings, showing a general agreement between the two techniques.

In addition, altimeter data from ERS and TOPEX/Poseidon satellites, obtained during the period from 1992 to 1998, were analyzed in order to estimate geostrophic currents in the study area. Sea level anomaly data from altimeter can be used to calculate seasonal eddy kinetic energy and 10-day averaged geostrophic velocity anomalies presented as gridded data on maps. Geostrophic velocity anomalies from an altimeter track located near current meter moorings were correlated with current measurements over a three year period. The highest correlation of 0.65 was found between current at 300 m depth and altimeter points located about 30 km from the mooring.

Preliminary comparisons between the SAR and altimeter results indicate that there is qualitative agreement between interpolated velocity vectors from altimeter and instantaneous current pattern observed in SAR imagery. The time and spatial scales of the two methods are different, however, which makes it difficult to perform accurate comparisons.

The study showed that satellite SAR and altimeter data can play an important role to obtain synoptic information about current regimes over larger areas, which is complementary to standard buoy measurements at fixed locations and model simulations.

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1 Introduction

The offshore petroleum exploration is moving from the Norwegian Continental Shelf (NCS) at water depths of 200 – 400 m to the continental slope areas with depths from 500 to more than 2000 m. The offshore industry in Norway has instituted a joint meteorological and oceanographical (metocean) project within the Norwegian Deepwater Programme in connection with opening of new licenses in deep waters off Mid-Norway. The metocean conditions of these areas are generally more extreme than at the NCS because of the greater exposure to the Atlantic Ocean and the Norwegian Sea. One of the aims of the metocean project is to obtain knowledge about current conditions required for design and operation of floating structures. Use of satellite altimeter and SAR data is part of the observation programme in this project.

The specified study area is west of mid-Norway approximately from 62° to 67° N (Figure 1a).

Figure 1. (a) Map of the study area showing isobaths of 500 m, 1000 m, 2000 m and 3000 m. The squares indicate location of ERS-2 SAR scenes used in the study. (b) Example of ERS-2 image 30 May 1998, covering 100 by 100 km, showing fronts and eddy structures visible as curved lines, especially in the left part of the image. ©ESA/TSS, 1998.

The region's complicated bathymetry, combined with strong ocean currents and presence of a front between Norwegian Atlantic Current and the Norwegian Coastal Current makes it an area of high mesoscale variability, with generation of meanders and eddies representing the maximum current velocities. Hence, regular monitoring over an extended period of time is necessary to obtain reliable statistics on the current regime, including mesoscale eddy activity. This area is also subject to severe wave conditions, exposed to propagation of long-

period waves from the North Atlantic, interacting with the ocean currents, creating confused seas with wave heights higher than can be attributed to ambient weather conditions.

Satellite remote sensing techniques for observation of meteorological and oceanographical phenomena have developed rapidly in the last 10 years (Johannessen et al., 1999). For many years satellite data were limited to optical and infrared sensors which could mainly be used to observe clouds and surface temperature as part of the global meteorological observations system. With the development of microwave radar techniques it is now possible to observe and quantify several processes and phenomena at the sea surface such as waves, winds, fronts, eddies, currents, slicks and atmospheric boundary layer processes.

The main advantage of satellite data is the capability of synoptic observations over large areas. When these synoptic observations are coordinated with *in situ* wind, wave and current measurements optimal data sets can be established to characterize meteorological and oceanographical conditions over large ocean areas.

2 Analysis of Synthetic Aperture Radar images

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images from the European Space Agency's ERS-2 satellite have been used to map the location of current fronts and eddies and their characteristic scale and rotation in the study area (Figure 1a). Attempts were made to use Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) data from the NOAA 12 and 14 satellites to map sea surface temperature, including temperature fronts and eddies, simultaneously with acquisition of SAR data. But very few such images were found because cloud cover dominated the study area. Details of the study and its results are reported in the report by Sandven et al. (1998).

The available SAR archive at Tromsø Satellite Station was investigated finding 63 scenes providing useful information about surface features for the study area in the period from November 1996 to June 1998. Useful scenes were most numerous in spring and summer when the wind conditions were calculated to moderate which is required for SAR imaging of ocean features. The selected scenes of 100 km x 100 km each were concentrated to form images on 33 different days, each image composed of 1-4 successive scenes. This was less than 50 % of all available SAR images in this area. The remaining images could not be used because they were dominated by high wind and other atmosphere effects masking out the surface features. Another factor which limits the number of available images is the fact that SAR data are only obtained on request, which means that there are many orbits without image acquisition. The results of the image analysis are shown in Table 1.

The spatial distribution of SAR observation in the study area is non-homogeneous, because there is no systematic acquisition of images. Therefore, we have estimated for each square of 0.5° latitude and 1° longitude the number of images and the number of fronts, eddies and current patterns by manual interpretation. This is used to find the relative occurrence of feature observations which is total number of observed fronts and eddy features in each square divided by number of SAR images within the square (Figure 3). The SAR ocean surface features can be divided into two main groups:

- 1) Fronts or eddies are seen as curved dark or bright current related line features without occurrence of slicks. The background usually has the same backscatter level on both sides of the feature. Line features can be caused by zones of current shear or by current convergence/divergence, which affect the capillary waves and thereby the SAR backscatter (Johannessen et al., 1996). An example of this type of image is shown in Figure 1b.
- 2) Elongated dark lines of slicks show surface current patterns including eddies without clear fronts. Biological surface material generate slicks which act as tracers for the water motion, especially in the spring and summer. An example of this type of image is shown in Figure 2.

Table 1. Features seen in the SAR images.

Image no.	Image date	Ocean fronts					Current pattern without fronts		Eddies			Comments
		# of fronts	length (km)	orientation	Bright Front	dark front	turbulent field	orientation	# cyclonic	# anti-cyclonic	scale (km)	
1	10.11.96	no					no		-	-		only atmospheric features mainly atmospheric features
2	29.11.96	1	30	N-S	X		no		-	-		
3	19.01.97	15-20	5-100	NW-SE SW-NE	many	a few	no		-	-		
4	14.03.97	8-12	5-80	SW-NE	many	a few	no		-	-		eddies visible due to slicks most of image covered by winds turbulent eddy field dominates > 5 well-defined eddies, internal waves well-defined eddies
5	07.05.97	10-20	5-30	all	many	a few	no	EW + all	3 - 5	1	5 - 30	
6	23.05.97	3-5	10-50	N-S	X	X	no		2	-	10 - 20	
7	01.06.97	3-5	10-20	N-S	-	X	yes	all	3 - 4	1	10 - 30	
8	08.06.97	2-3	10-20	E-W	X	X	yes	all	7 - 8	1 - 2	5 - 30	
9	11.06.97	no					yes	all	8 - 10	3 - 4	10 - 40	
10	19.06.97	no					yes	all	3	-	5 - 40	
11	13.07.97	no					yes	all	yes	yes	> 5	
12	16.07.97	4-6	20-30	N-S E-W	-	X	yes	all	6 - 7	1 - 2	10 - 50	
13	19.07.97	3-5	20-50	N-S E-W	-	X	little		5 - 6	-	10 - 40	
14	01.08.97	3-5	20-30	N-S	X	X	yes	all	3 - 4	-	20 - 30	
15	30.08.97	10-15	20-50	N-S	many	-	no	SE - NW	2 - 3	-	5 - 10	
16	24.09.97	8-10	20-40	all	X	X	no		4 - 5	-	10 - 20	
17	27.09.97	10-12	10-100	SW-NE	X	X	little	S - N	3 - 4	-	10 - 20	
18	22.12.97	> 20	10-50	all	X	X	little	all	4 - 5	-	10 - 30	
19	15.01.98	6-8	10-50	all	X	X	little		1	-	20	
20	26.01.98	6-8	10-50	all	X	X	no		-	-		
21	24.02.98	5-6	20-50	SW-NE NW-SE	X	X	no		-	-		
22	02.03.98	4-5	10-40	all	X	-	no		-	-	internal waves	
23	08.03.98	6-8	20-50	SW-NE NW-SE	X	X	no		1	-	20	
24	19.04.98	no					yes	all	5 - 6	-	5 - 20	
25	19.04.98	4-5	10-50	all	X	X	no		3 - 4	-	10 - 20	
26	22.04.98	no					yes	all	6 - 7	-	10 - 30	
27	05.05.98	4-5	10-30	E-W			little	all	5 - 6	1 - 2	10 - 20	
28	08.05.98	no					yes	all	4 - 5	-	10 - 30	
29	16.05.98	2-3	20-30	NW-SE	X	X	little	EW	2 - 3	1	5 - 30	
30	30.05.98	4-5	20-50	NW-SE	X	-	little	SW-NE	2 - 3	-	10 - 20	
31	12.06.98	3-4	20-30	all	X	X	yes	all	-	-		
32	12.06.98	4-5	20-50	ALL			no		1	0	30	
33	24.06.98	no					little		0	1	30	

Figure 2. (left) ERS-2 SAR image covering the Ormen Lange field, obtained on 22 April 1998, showing intense eddy activity. Note the stronger backscatter signal area in the lower left part of the image caused by stronger wind here. ©ESA/TSS, 1998; (right) AVHRR image obtained on 21 April 1998, and current fronts and eddy features observed in the SAR image.

Figure 3. Spatial distribution of SAR images (left), fronts observed in them (middle) and the relative frequency of front occurrence (right).

The main results of the SAR image analysis are:

- 1) Ocean fronts were seen in about 75 % of the SAR images, with a typical length of 20-40 km. In about half of these images, the fronts were oriented in 1-2 predominant directions (NW-SE and SW-NW).
- 2) Current patterns due to slicks were observed in nearly 60 % of the SAR images. The current patterns showing the mesoscale flow field were most frequently found from April to August, since slicks are observed more frequently in the spring and summer. The orientation of the features appeared to be random.
- 3) Eddies were observed in about 75 % of the SAR images. Typical horizontal scale of the eddies was 10-30 km, and the rotation was cyclonic for most of the eddies. In one case the mean propagation speed over a 3-day period could be estimated to 18 cm/s for one cyclonic eddy.
- 4) Comparison of satellite observed features with bottom topography showed that the maximum occurrence of fronts and eddies was found along the shelf break from 62.5° N to 65° N and from 66.5° N to 67.5° N. This area coincides with the core of the North-Atlantic current as observed by a moored current meter array (Skagseth et al., 1998).

A comparison of current patterns in SAR images with in situ current measurements from Aanderaa moorings is described in Chapter 5.

3 Analysis of altimeter data

The altimeter is a nadir-looking active microwave instrument which transmits short pulses from the satellite to the sea surface and accurately clocks the time elapsed before the reflected pulses are received at the altimeter antenna. The distance from the antenna to the sea surface is then computed using estimates for the speed of light through the intervening atmospheric column. This distance is subtracted from the height of the antenna above a chosen reference ellipsoid to obtain the height of the sea surface above the ellipsoid. The major unknown components of the sea surface topography estimated in this way are the geoid undulations and the dynamic topography which is related to ocean current features at different spatial and temporal scales (Figure 4). In this study ERS and TOPEX/Poseidon altimeter data have been used.

Figure 4. The satellite altimeter measurement principle.

The TOPEX/Poseidon altimeter, which provide the most accurate sea level estimates so far, has instrumental accuracies better than 2 cm (P.Y. Le Traon et al., 1997). However, errors in the determination of the orbit height and the effect on the speed of light due to various environmental factors, such as water vapour in the atmosphere, degrade the accuracy of the estimated altimetric sea level.

Since the geoid is not known to sufficient accuracy in most cases, at wavelengths shorter than 1000 km, the normal procedure is to subtract the sea surface height (topography) measurement at a selected time from all other measurements at the same point to obtain the sea level anomalies (SLA). This eliminates the geoid component from the sea level since it is time-invariant, but unfortunately, also the time-invariant part of the dynamic sea level. The temporal mean of the measurements at each point is subsequently subtracted from the instantaneous height residuals to obtain the sea level anomaly referred to the mean sea level. The sea level anomaly thus computed is a very good indicator of mesoscale variability of the ocean current field and provides quantitative information about the location, strength and size of eddies, meanders and fronts, the weakening and strengthening of currents and other mesoscale features. Under the geostrophic assumption, it is also possible to estimate the velocity anomalies from the gradient of the height anomalies, and subsequently, the eddy kinetic energy.

In the simplest case, the dynamic sea level derived from altimeter measurements may be related to the surface current field through the geostrophic equation, which describe non-accelerated motion where the pressure gradient is balanced by the Coriolis force (Figure 5). In this case, the role of other forces such as wind stress, bottom friction and viscous forces are negligible.

Figure 5. Balance of forces for a geostrophic current directed into the paper.

The equation of motion then reduces to:

$$-fv = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

$$fu = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \quad (2)$$

$$\rho g = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} \quad (3)$$

where p is the pressure, u , v , are the x - and y - components respectively, of the current velocity, ρ is the density, g the gravitational acceleration, f is the Coriolis parameter, given by $f = 2 \times \Omega \times \sin O$, where Ω is the earth's angular velocity and O is the latitude. Integrating Eq 3 and substituting in Eq 1 and Eq 2 gives

$$v = -\frac{g}{f} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial x}$$

$$u = \frac{g}{f} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial y}$$

where ζ is the height of the sea surface. Thus geostrophic velocities are related to the sea surface slopes in a direction normal to the currents. For a typical western boundary current, with a current speed of 1 ms^{-1} , surface slopes are of the order of 1 m per 100 km.

In the case of mesoscale eddies and meanders, the geostrophic balance will be modified by the centrifugal forces resulting from the curvature of the flow field.

$$v_{\theta r} = -\frac{rf}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{r^2 f^2}{4} + rg} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial r}$$

where r is the radius of curvature. For the same sea surface slopes, gradient current speeds are higher than geostrophic current speeds when the flow is anticyclonic motion and lower than geostrophic current speeds when the flow is cyclonic.

Wind stresses, bottom friction, viscous forces, etc complicates the balance of forces and give rise to accelerated motion. However, in such cases where the geostrophic balance does not strictly apply, the surface slopes can be used to extract the geostrophic component of the total current velocity.

Most altimeter missions have been exact repeat missions where the complete ground track pattern is laid out within a selected repeat period or cycle. During subsequent cycles the ground track pattern is repeated so that each data point is sampled at intervals corresponding to the repeat period. Excursions from the pre-determined nominal ground track are restricted to within 1 km. The ground track forms a lattice of ascending (north-going) and descending (south-going) tracks. Sea level measurements are averaged and recorded at approximately 1 second intervals during which time the satellite will have covered 7 km along the ground track. Since the altimeter is a nadir-viewing instrument providing a single averaged observation from each along-track data point with a footprint size of the order of a few kilometers, there will be significant gaps in the coverage due to the finite distance between adjacent passes. The cross-track spacing increases when the repeat period is decreased and vice versa, so that there is a tradeoff between the spatial resolution and temporal resolution. However, the cross-track spacing is also latitude-dependent, decreasing towards higher latitudes (Figure 6).

By combining data from both ERS and TOPEX/Poseidon data available since 1992, it has been possible to produce seven years of gridded data approximately at 10 km resolution and with a time interval of 10 days (Haugen et al., 1998). The main improvements in this data set, compared to previous analyses of altimeter data, are that the environmental and other corrections used are consistent between the ERS and TOPEX/Poseidon data sets. In addition, an objective analysis technique, which takes into account the spatial and temporal covariances in the data set, has been employed to interpolate both ERS and TOPEX/Poseidon data to a common grid to produce a combined data set.

(a) ERS 35-day repeat

(b) TOPEX/Poseidon 10-day repeat

Figure 6. Ground tracks during one repeat period for the data sets used. The respective repeat periods are indicated. Sea level is sampled at ~7 km along the track.

3.1 *Maps of eddy kinetic energy*

The seasonal distributions of eddy kinetic energy (EKE) computed from the merged ERS and TOPEX/Poseidon data provide an indication of areas with enhanced mesoscale current activity, in the form of eddies, fronts, meandering currents as well as variations in the strengths of the current. Distribution maps of EKE calculated for three months averaged data from 1993 to 1998 are shown in Figure 7. These maps show high values (above $100 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) along the path of the Norwegian Atlantic Current, with maximum values (up to $200 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) within the Feroe-Shetland Channel. This is to be expected, as mesoscale activity is generally higher in the neighborhood of strong currents, which often interact with the topography to generate meanders and eddies. It is particularly interesting to note that altimetry detects high EKE to the north of the Faroe Islands, confirming the recent observations of significant inflow of Atlantic water around the islands (Hansen et al., 1986). In the Norwegian Sea, there are pockets of high EKE centered around $63^\circ\text{N}; 5^\circ\text{E}$ and $64.5^\circ\text{N}; 3.5^\circ\text{E}$. These regions overlap the locations of the deep water licensing areas, (Ormen Lange, More Vest and Helland Hansen) where also the SAR images showed high eddy activity. The EKE is low over most of the deep basin of the Norwegian Sea, the northern reaches of the North Sea and in the near-shore areas north of 64°N .

The seasonal variability in the EKE distributions shows a tendency for enhanced activity over large parts of the study area in the winter period (October – March) compared to the summer period (April -September). However, while EKE is high overall during January-March, these high values persist only in the Norwegian Sea during April-June. In the neighborhood of the Faroe Islands, high EKE is limited to very narrow pockets, spreading to the north of the Faroe Islands. The overall picture shows enhanced mesoscale activity in the Feroe-Shetland Channel during July-September, moving northwards with the Norwegian Atlantic Current to extend over most of its path including the retroflection southwards along the Norwegian coast in January-March.

OPERALT
Kinetic Energy from T/P and ERS-1/2
Jan-Mar 1993 to 1998

OPERALT
Kinetic Energy from T/P and ERS-1/2
Apr-Jun 1993 to 1998

Figure 7. Averaged eddy kinetic energy from altimeter data for July – September 1993 – 1998. Courtesy: C. Boone, CLS.

OPERALT
Kinetic Energy from T/P and ERS-1/2
Jul-Sep 1993 to 1998

OPERALT
Kinetic Energy from T/P and ERS-1/2
Oct-Dec 1992 to 1997

Figure 7. continued

3.2 Maps of the distribution of Reynolds Stresses

The gridded data set of sea level anomalies also allows examination of the directional properties of the mesoscale variability. This is presented in the Reynolds Stress distributions for the 4 seasons as presented in Figure 8. The arrows represent the direction along which variability is maximum (direction of principal variance) and the direction normal to it at each grid cell which is about 50 x 50 km, with the length of the arrows indicating the magnitude of the variances. In an isotropic field, the magnitude of the variance would be equal in all directions. The plots in Figure 8, however, show a significant degree of anisotropy, as would be expected in an area dominated by a relatively strong current. In the Norwegian Sea, there is a clear tendency for the directions of principal variance to be aligned along the depth contours along the core of the Norwegian Atlantic Current. This could be interpreted to imply that the position of the core current is relatively fixed, with variability being mainly due to strengthening and weakening of the mean current, rather than due to meanders. Towards the seaward edges of the current, the variances are lower, and the field is more isotropic, an indication of the meandering nature of the current here. This is also the case in the Færoe-Shetland Channel, where the mesoscale variability is large, but more or less isotropic, indicating that the current does not have a narrow and steady core here as is the case further northwards.

The only seasonal differences in the Reynolds Stress distribution is in the magnitude of the variability, rather than in the directionality. In the Færoe-Shetland Channel, isotropy seems to become more evident during July to December.

Theory of Reynolds stress:

The Reynolds stress is a stress exerted by the turbulent fluctuation on the mean flow. It can also be interpreted as the rate of mean momentum transfer by turbulent fluctuations.

If the turbulent fluctuations are completely isotropic, if they have no directional preference, the off-diagonal components of $\overline{u'v'}$ vanish, and $\overline{u'^2} = \overline{v'^2} = \overline{w'^2}$.

Reynolds equation for x-component of velocity:

$$\frac{d\bar{u}}{dt} = -\alpha \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x} + 2\Omega \sin \phi \bar{v} - 2\Omega \cos \phi \bar{w} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \overline{u'u'} - \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \overline{u'v'} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \overline{u'w'}$$

A term such as $\nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}}{\partial x^2} \right)$ can be written as $\partial / (\nu \partial \bar{u} / \partial x) \partial x$, and $\rho \nu (\partial \bar{u} / \partial x)$ is the stress in the

direction due to molecular effects and a gradient of \bar{u} in the x-direction. We can therefore identify $-\rho \overline{u'u'}$ as a stress due to the turbulence, termed Reynolds stresses.

Figure 8. Reynolds Stress from altimeter data for July – September 1993 – 1998. Courtesy: C. Boone, CLS.

Figure 8. Continued

3.3 Time series of repeated altimeter tracks.

In addition to estimating long-term averaged EKE and Reynolds stresses it is useful to study time variability of individual altimeter tracks. In Figure 9a the SSH anomalies along 150 km of track 144 of TOPEX/Poseidon are shown for a period from July to November 1997. This section of track 144 is taken south of Ormen Lange, in an area where the dominant currents are perpendicular to the altimeter tracks. The cross track velocity anomalies estimated from the slope of the SSH anomalies are shown for the same tracks in Figure 9b. The same parameters can also be presented as contour plots (Figure 9c and d). Positive and negative anomalies appear regularly along the track and it is difficult to isolate any of these as being more dominant than others.

If an eddy propagates through such a track at a speed which can be resolved by the 10 day repeat cycle of TOPEX/Poseidon, it should be possible to recognize this propagation in the repeat tracks. These plots do not indicate any regular features which could be attributed to any eddy propagation. This could be due to the fact that eddies propagate faster than what is possible to recognize with 10 day repeat cycle, or that the anomalies are caused by other processes than eddies.

a

b

c

d

Figure 9. The along-track sea level anomalies and cross-track velocity anomalies along track 144.

3.4 Ten-day averaged maps of SLA overlaid with geostrophic velocity anomaly vectors

The along track sea level anomalies can be gridded onto regular space-time grids, where the cross track spacing and the repeat period are used to determine appropriate grid sizes. For TOPEX/Poseidon these can be presented as ten days averaged maps of sea level anomalies overlaid with geostrophic velocity vectors calculated from the sea surface slopes (Figure 10).

The anomalies presents a chaotic picture, but we can observe a general tendency for positive anomalies to be more frequently generated in the western part of the plot area, over the continental slope, which has a sharp bend in this region. These anomalies may be related to anticyclonic eddies generated at the frontal boundary between the coastal waters and the Norwegian Atlantic Current due to the topographic effects. The current velocities computed using the geostrophic equation have magnitudes of the order of 10-20 cm/s.

a) Topex/Poseidon 26 December 1996

b) 5 January 1997

c) TOPEX/Poseidon 15 January 1997

d) 25 January 1997

Figure 10. Ten-day averaged maps of SLA overlaid with geostrophic velocity anomaly vectors.

4 Intercomparison of altimeter and SAR

A direct comparison between altimeter derived currents and SAR image features is difficult because the temporal and spatial coverage and resolution of the two systems are quite different. While SAR is capable of observing snapshots of features with scales down to a few hundreds of meters, the altimeter provides sea level heights along the satellite tracks with a sampling distance of about 7 km. By combining data from several tracks over a time interval of at least 10 days, it is possible to establish geostrophic velocity anomaly maps resolving current features with scales of a few tens of kilometers. This implies that the altimeter can observe current features which are persistent and stationary over at least 10 days. Altimeter data can not capture short-lived mesoscale features observed by SAR. On the other hand, the temporal SAR sampling, which is at best three days, is not good enough to follow the evolution of the short-lived features.

The temporal sampling is also a problem in deriving the altimeter sea level anomalies. The lack of an adequate geoid makes it necessary to subtract a temporal mean from the altimeter height measurements. The 10 (35) day sampling interval of the TOPEX/Poseidon (ERS) altimeter is hardly adequate to resolve mesoscale variability in the study area, where temporal scales of eddies can be as short as a few days. Consequently, the mean that is subtracted from the time series of sea level measurements will be contaminated by variability at these unresolved temporal scales.

Since SAR is a side-looking instrument and altimeter is a nadir-looking instrument, it is not feasible to obtain simultaneous observations from the two instruments from the same satellite. In our case, it has been possible to use altimeter tracks of the T/P crossing ERS-2 SAR swath within 1-2 days of each other. This approach has been used to compare SAR current features imaged with geostrophic current estimates from altimeter.

Case 1

The ERS-2 SAR image which was acquired at 21:32 Z on June 19th near the Ormen Lange field, is shown in Figure 11. The left part of the image is dominated by a uniform area without clear structures at the surface. In the right part, the presence of slicks makes it possible to identify a cyclonic eddy which is 20-30 km in diameter. A few smaller eddies are also seen in the lower right part of the image. There was a T/P altimeter track over the image area three days earlier (16 June). The sea level anomalies and the cross-track geostrophic current from the 16 June track are superimposed on the SAR image. Also the averaged geostrophic velocity vector field based on all tracks over the 10-day period from the 13 to the 23 June is superimposed on the image.

This is one example where there is reasonable good consistency between current features in the SAR image and calculated currents from the altimeter data. The current field from the altimeter data shows a cyclonic eddy near the center of the image, while the eddy in the SAR image is displaced some 30 km to the northeast, which can be interpreted as a propagation of the eddy. The current components from the single altimeter track also shows that there is a cyclonic circulation with minimum velocity in the center of the eddy. The fact that the eddy shows up clearly in the 10-day averaged velocity field suggests that the eddy has been fairly stationary sitting in the same area for several days.

Figure 11. ERS-2 SAR image acquired on 19.06.97 overlaid with altimeter along-track anomalies (coloured dots), and cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies (green arrows) on 16.06.97 and mapped geostrophic velocity anomalies (red arrows) for the period 13.06.97 to 23.06.97.

Case 2

The ERS-2 SAR image acquired on July 16, 1997 near the Helland-Hansen – Ormen-Lange area is shown in Figure 12. It shows two cyclonic eddies, made visible by the presence of slicks. The TOPEX/Poseidon altimeter Track 118 crosses the location of the lower eddy two days later on 18.07.97, but seems to indicate an anticyclonic circulation there. The mapped geostrophic velocity anomalies for the period 13.07.97 to 23.07.97 also show an anticyclonic circulation in this area. At the location of the northernmost eddy, a cyclonic circulation is indicated, although it is difficult to see whether it is an eddy or just a meander.

Figure 12. ERS-2 SAR image acquired on 16.07.97 overlaid with altimeter along-track anomalies (coloured dots), and cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies (green arrows) on

18.07.97 and mapped geostrophic velocity anomalies (red arrows) for the period 13.07.97 to 23.07.97.

Case 3

The ERS-2 SAR image acquired on July 19th, 1997 is shown in Figure 13. It overlaps the image described in the previous section and it appears as though the two cyclonic eddies observed then have propagated northeastwards. The TOPEX/Poseidon altimeter Track 139 crosses in the vicinity of the southernmost eddy about 4 hours after the SAR acquisition time, and shows negative sea level anomalies and a cyclonic velocity anomaly structure. The mapped velocity anomalies for the period 13.07.97 to 23.07.97 also show a cyclonic circulation at the location of this eddy. However, further north, the circulation patterns do not agree with the SAR image. It has to be remembered that the mapped anomalies represent an average over 10 days, and in a situation where there is significant eddy propagation during this period, one would not expect to find close correspondence with an instantaneous SAR image.

Figure 13. ERS-2 SAR image acquired on 19.07.97 overlaid with altimeter along-track anomalies (coloured dots), and cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies (green arrows) on 19.07.97 and mapped geostrophic velocity anomalies (red arrows) for the period 13.07.97 to 23.07.97.

Case 4

The ERS-2 SAR image acquired over an area southwest of Ormen Lange is shown in Figure 14. It shows very clear frontal structures, oriented in a northwesterly direction.

TOPEX/Poseidon altimeter Track 144 crosses these features about 6 hours before the SAR image was taken and indicates a front zone with southward velocities on the left and northward velocities on the right. The averaged mapped geostrophic velocity field shows a cyclonic eddy in the lower part of the image which agrees with the instantaneous data from the altimeter track.

Figure 14. ERS-2 SAR image acquired on 27.09.97 overlaid with altimeter along-track anomalies (coloured dots), and cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies (green arrows) on 27.09.97 and mapped geostrophic velocity anomalies (red arrows) for the period 21.09.97 to 01.10.97.

5 Comparison between SAR and current measurements

An array of four moorings with Aanderaa current meters for several years have been operated by Geophysical Institute, University of Bergen along the Svinøy Section (SS) off the Møre coast for several years. The current measurements between October 96 and October 97 have been documented in Data reports no. VI -VIII (Skagseth et al. 1995 -1997), and data obtained after October 97 have been provided. by personal communication. The current meters have been deployed at depths of 100m, 300m and near the bottom.

Other current meters moorings have also been operative for several shorter periods of a few months each along sections near Ormen Lange, Møre West , Helland Hansen, Vema/Nyk and Gjallar. These data have been documented by Mathisen, 1998.

In this study, current data taken at the same time and location as the SAR images are extracted and compared with features in the SAR images. Data from the uppermost current meter, usually at 100 m depth, has been used in the comparison. The position and depths of the seven current meters correspond in time and area with one or more SAR scenes, shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of current meters used for comparison with SAR images. SS: Svinøy section, OL: Ormen Lange section.

Section incidents	Mooring Id	Position	Bottom depth	Meas. Depth
SS	S1	62.81°N 04.26°E	500 m	100 m
SS	S2	62.89°N 04.06°E	700 m	100 m
SS	X1/E1	63.00°N 03.89°E	900 m	100 m
SS	X2/E2	63.11°N 03.66°E	1000 m	100 m
OL	1	63.50°N 05.67°E	415 m	90 m
OL	2	63.53°N 05.46°E	800 m	100 m
OL	3	63.60°N 05.24°E	1090 m	200 m

A total of eleven incidents have been identified where a SAR image and the buoy measurements are coincident (Table 3), six of which are cases when SAR images indicate features of interest.

Table 3. Summary of cases with coincident SAR and current measurements.

Case	Date	Array	Remark on SAR features.
	10 November 1996	OL	No certain current features in image
	29 November 1996	OL	Only wind features near buoy pos.
1	07 May 1997	SS	Many current fronts near buoy pos.
2	11 June 1997	SS	Many eddy lines near buoy pos.
3	11 June 1997	OL	Many eddy lines near buoy pos.
4	19 June 1997	SS	Lines forming large eddies near buoy pos.
	16 July 1997	SS	Uniform area near buoy pos. (no lines).
5	24 September 1997	SS	Many current fronts near buoy pos.
6	27 September 1997	SS	Many current fronts near buoy pos.
	02 Marsh 1998	SS	Only wind features near buoy pos.
	22 April 1998	SS	Only wind features near buoy pos.

The cases where certain current-related features are seen on SAR near the buoy positions are described in more detail with current vectors superimposed on the SAR images

Case 1. Svinøy section, 7 May 1997.

The SAR image (Figure 15a) shows many current fronts in the mooring area, but they are not related to any clear eddy features. At S1 the current was 15 cm/s in direction 60° in an area of weak frontal features. S2 observed 35 cm/s in direction 60° , at almost right angle to another weak front. At E1 the current was 15 cm/s in direction 340° in an area where no fronts are seen. The correspondence between fronts and currents is inconclusive.

Case 2. Svinøy section, 11 June 1997

The SAR image (Figure 15b) shows low wind and many slick lines and small eddies. A well defined cyclonic eddy is seen with its center 15 km north of S1. Current observations at S1 was 40 cm/s in direction 70° , and at S2 50 cm/s in direction 90° . The observed direction, are in good agreement with the line features in the SAR image. E1 measured 10 cm/s in direction 270° in an area without clear features.

a) Case 1. 7 May 1997

b) Case 2. 11 June 1997

Figure 15 . Case 1 and Case 2. SAR images overlaid with current vectors obtained at the same time as the SAR image The long arrow indicates the north direction.

Case 3. Ormen Lange section, 11 June 1997.

Another well defined cyclonic eddy on the same low-wind SAR stripe as shown in Case 2 is seen southwest of the three Ormen Lange moorings (Figure 16a). In this area, OL1 measured 15 cm/s in direction 0° , OL2 measured 40 cm/s in direction 350° , and OL3 measured 40 cm/s in direction 330° . These directions are all in good agreement with the line features defining the eddy in the SAR image.

Case 4. Svinøy section, 19 June 1997.

The SAR image (Figure 16b) shows a larger cyclonic eddy north of the 3 current moorings and a smaller cyclonic eddy between S2 and E1. S2 measured 40 cm/s in direction 45° , which is about 30° clockwise relative to the direction of the current-lines southeast of the eddy center. E1 measured

15 cm/s in direction 270° , which is in good agreement with the current lines north of the same eddy. E2 measured 15 cm/s in direction 260° in an area without clear line features.

a) Case 3. 11 June 1997

b) Case 4. 19 June 1997

Figure 16. Case 3 and Case 4. SAR images overlaid with current vectors obtained at the same time as the SAR image. The long arrow indicates the north direction.

Case 5. Svinøy section, 24 September 1997.

The SAR image (Figure 17a) shows a few current fronts to the south of the moorings. S1 measured 15 cm/s in direction 70° and S2 measured 60 cm/s in direction 80° . Both directions are roughly parallel to the ocean front seen to the southwest of the moorings. E1 measured 5 cm/s in direction 60° in an area without clear features in the image.

Case 6. Svinøy section, 27 September 1997.

The SAR image (Figure 17b) shows several current fronts, mostly south of the mooring area. S2 measured 40 cm/s in direction 75° parallel to a near-by front. E1 measured 20 cm/s in direction 90° , while E2 measured 10 cm/s at direction 90° in areas without features.

a) Case 5. 24 September 1997

b) Case 6. 27 September 1997

Figure 17. Case 5 and Case 6. SAR images overlaid with current vectors obtained at the same time as the SAR image. The long arrow indicates the north direction.

In three of the cases (2, 3 and 4) well-defined mesoscale eddies are seen in the SAR image. These are clearly defined by slick lines on the ocean surface. For these cases, the correspondence between the SAR eddy line direction and the current meter direction is generally quite good, within about 30° of each other. Five of the current speed measurements were made at distances of 10 - 15 km from the eddy center, showing current speeds of 40 - 50 cm/s. One buoy (E1 in case 4) is only 5 km from the eddy center, with a speed measured to

be 15 cm/s. These are all reasonable values for an eddy orbital motion with increasing speed away from the eddy center, previously documented by Johannessen et al. (1989).

The three other cases (1, 5 and 6) did not show clear eddy features in the vicinity of the current moorings. Current frontal features observed near the mooring indicated that the frontal direction agreed with current measurements.

The conclusion of this comparison is that there is remarkable good agreement between current observations at 100 m depth and the surface features. It would be expected that the vertical current profiles had stronger shear. These observations suggest that the upper 100 m has quite uniform current profiles.

6 Comparison of altimeter analysis with current data

For a validation of altimeter derived geostrophic currents, an optimal field data set with observations spatially close to the altimeter tracks is required. Time series of current measurements should cover at least one year, so that the annual mean can be eliminated in the same way that the mean is subtracted from the altimeter data. In addition, since it is not obvious what depth layer the geostrophic velocities derived from the altimeter sea level anomalies represent, it is necessary to have current measurements from different depths.

The best available data set for the validation was the current meter data collected by the Geophysical Institute, University of Bergen, from four current meter moorings along the so-called Svinøy Section off the Møre coast of Norway. This is an area where the confluence in the shelf break result in a merging of different branches of the Atlantic inflow to the Norwegian Sea and the section cuts through the core of this inflow. The measurements began in April 1995 and have continued on a regular basis since then (Skagseth, Orvik and Mork, 1997).

The current meter data taken at the same time as the altimeter measurement along TOPEX/Poseidon Track 42 were extracted from the full time series after removing the main tidal components. The temporal mean of the current meter data was computed and subtracted from the time series. Subsequently, the component of the current vector in the direction normal to the altimeter track was computed. The altimeter cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies at 13 data points along the track were then calculated along with the cross-track velocity anomalies extracted from the 4 current meter moorings for different depths. A cross-correlation analysis was carried out between several altimeter and current mooring time series. The locations of the current meter moorings and the altimeter data points used in the comparison are shown in Figure 18. The results of the correlation analysis are shown in tabular form for the 4 different moorings in Tables 4 to 7. The current meter measurements are denoted by the mooring name and the depth of the current meter (for example, s1-100 is the current meter measurement at 100 m depth from mooring S1). The altimeter data points are denoted by the point number along TOPEX/Poseidon Track 42 followed by v (for example, 06v is altimeter point 6). The cross-correlation between s1-100 and 06v is given in the row corresponding to s1-100 and the column corresponding to 06v.

The correlation coefficients between the altimeter geostrophic velocities and the cross track velocity component from the current meters are not particularly high. The highest correlation seen is 0.65 between s1-300 and 07v and 08v. In contrast, the cross-correlation between time series from the same mooring (e1-100 and e1-300) is 0.89 and that between adjacent altimeter data points (08v and 09v) is 0.94. This is only to be expected in view of 1) the distance between the moorings and the altimeter data points which is 20 km or more, 2) the spatial averaging over several kms implicitly carried out in the altimeter and 3) the fact that the altimeter measurement is based on the geostrophic approximation, while the current meter measures the total current.

Apart from the low cross-correlation coefficients, however, there are some interesting characteristics in the structure of the cross-correlation matrix. The most obvious is that the correlation is significantly higher for altimeter data points which are approximately over the

Figure 18 Location of the current meter moorings S1, S2, E1 and E2 and the altimeter data points 5 to 18 along Topex/Poseidon Track 42, in relation to the depth

same depth contours as the current meter. For instance, for S1, best correlation is obtained for 6, 7 & 8, which may be seen from Figure 18 to be over approximately the same depth contour as S1. For S2, which is deployed in a little deeper water, best correlation is obtained for points 7, 8 & 9. For E1, the best correlation is obtained for points 9, 10 & 11, and for E2, points 11, 12 & 13 provide the best correlation. In at least some of the cases, these are not the altimeter data points that are closest in distance to the mooring in question. This is an important result, because it supports the hypothesis that the currents in this region are steered by the topography. The alignment of the altimeter pass is advantageous to the validation study, because the cross-track direction, along which the geostrophic velocities are computed are almost parallel to the depth contours. This implies that the cross-track velocity component contains the dominant part of the velocity vector.

Another interesting result is that the correlation with the altimeter data is consistently higher for the current meter measurements at 300 m depth than for the measurements at 100 m depth. In the case of mooring S2, the correlation for points 6, 7 & 8 are over 60 % higher (0.54 to 0.57) against the current meter at 300 m depth than against that at 100 m depth (0.33 to 0.35). The reason for this result is probably that the current meter measurements at 100 m depth are more affected by wind and other transient forcing which the altimeter processing

eliminate. Thus, despite being a sea surface measurement, sea level anomalies are representative of the current dynamics of the whole water column.

The velocity time series from one of the current meter moorings, S1 at depth 100 m and 300 m, and 2 altimeter data points 6 and 7 along TOPEX/Poseidon Track 42, which showed the best correlation are shown in Figure 19. It can be seen that the altimeter cross-track velocity anomalies generally fall within the range of variability of the current meter data and in most cases follow the peaks and valleys in the time series very well. A scatter plot of the current mooring S1 at depth 300 and altimeter data point 8 along TOPEX/Poseidon Track 42 is seen in Figure 20. These represented the current mooring and altimeter point of best correlation.

Figure 19. Time series of cross-track current anomalies from the current meter mooring S1 (depths 100 and 300 m) and altimeter data points 6-7 along TOPEX/Poseidon Track 42. The data covers a period of about 3 years.

Figure 20. Scatter plot of the current mooring S1 at depth 300 and altimeter data point 8 along TOPEX/Poseidon Track 42.

Table 4. Cross-correlation matrix for the current meter mooring S1 (depths 100, 300 & 480 m) and altimeter data points 5-11 along TOPEX/Poseidon track 42.

	s1-100	s1-300	s1-480	05v	06v	07v	08v	09v	10v	11v
s1-100	1.00	0.79	0.34	0.43	0.50	0.54	0.54	0.49	0.38	0.22
s1-300	0.79	1.00	0.56	0.57	0.62	0.65	0.65	0.60	0.47	0.26
s1-480	0.34	0.56	1.00	0.39	0.43	0.47	0.49	0.50	0.48	0.41
05v	0.43	0.57	0.39	1.00	0.97	0.86	0.66	0.40	0.16	-0.03
06v	0.50	0.62	0.43	0.97	1.00	0.96	0.81	0.58	0.32	0.07
07v	0.54	0.65	0.47	0.86	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.78	0.53	0.22
08v	0.54	0.65	0.49	0.66	0.81	0.94	1.00	0.94	0.74	0.43
09v	0.49	0.60	0.50	0.40	0.58	0.78	0.94	1.00	0.92	0.67
10v	0.38	0.47	0.48	0.16	0.32	0.53	0.74	0.92	1.00	0.89
11v	0.22	0.26	0.41	-0.03	0.07	0.22	0.43	0.67	0.89	1.00

Table 5. Cross-correlation matrix for the current meter mooring S2 (depths 100, & 300 m) and altimeter data points 5-12 along TOPEX/Poseidon track 42.

	s2-100	s2-300	05v	06v	07v	08v	09v	10v	11v	12v
s2-100	1.00	0.61	0.23	0.28	0.33	0.35	0.33	0.28	0.19	0.06
s2-300	0.61	1.00	0.41	0.48	0.55	0.57	0.54	0.45	0.29	0.10
05v	0.23	0.41	1.00	0.97	0.86	0.66	0.40	0.16	-0.03	-0.12
06v	0.28	0.48	0.97	1.00	0.96	0.81	0.58	0.32	0.07	-0.11
07v	0.33	0.55	0.86	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.78	0.53	0.22	-0.06
08v	0.35	0.57	0.66	0.81	0.94	1.00	0.94	0.74	0.43	0.05
09v	0.33	0.54	0.40	0.58	0.78	0.94	1.00	0.92	0.67	0.27
10v	0.28	0.45	0.16	0.32	0.53	0.74	0.92	1.00	0.89	0.57
11v	0.19	0.29	-0.03	0.07	0.22	0.43	0.67	0.89	1.00	0.87
12v	0.06	0.10	-0.12	-0.11	-0.06	0.05	0.27	0.57	0.87	1.00

Table 6. Cross-correlation matrix for the current meter mooring E1 (depths 100 & 300 m) and altimeter data points 5-13 along TOPEX/Poseidon track 42.

	e1-100	e1-300	05v	06v	07v	08v	09v	10v	11v	12v	13v
e1-100	1.00	0.89	0.22	0.26	0.30	0.33	0.34	0.36	0.36	0.31	0.19
e1-300	0.89	1.00	0.26	0.29	0.32	0.34	0.36	0.37	0.36	0.29	0.17
05v	0.22	0.26	1.00	0.97	0.86	0.66	0.40	0.16	-0.03	-0.12	-0.13
06v	0.26	0.29	0.97	1.00	0.96	0.81	0.58	0.32	0.07	-0.11	-0.19
07v	0.30	0.32	0.86	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.78	0.53	0.22	-0.06	-0.24
08v	0.33	0.34	0.66	0.81	0.94	1.00	0.94	0.74	0.43	0.05	-0.23
09v	0.34	0.36	0.40	0.58	0.78	0.94	1.00	0.92	0.67	0.27	-0.10
10v	0.36	0.37	0.16	0.32	0.53	0.74	0.92	1.00	0.89	0.57	0.17
11v	0.36	0.36	-0.03	0.07	0.22	0.43	0.67	0.89	1.00	0.87	0.55
12v	0.31	0.29	-0.12	-0.11	-0.06	0.05	0.27	0.57	0.87	1.00	0.88
13v	0.19	0.17	-0.13	-0.19	-0.24	-0.23	-0.10	0.17	0.55	0.88	1.00

Table 7. Cross-correlation matrix for the current meter mooring E2 (depths 100 & 300 m) and altimeter data points 7-15 along TOPEX/Poseidon track 42.

	e2-100	e2-300	07v	08v	09v	10v	11v	12v	13v	14v	15v
e2-100	1.00	0.86	0.14	0.15	0.21	0.32	0.48	0.56	0.51	0.39	0.22
e2-300	0.86	1.00	0.25	0.27	0.35	0.48	0.59	0.61	0.56	0.45	0.23
07v	0.14	0.25	1.00	0.94	0.78	0.53	0.22	-0.06	-0.24	-0.29	-0.26
08v	0.15	0.27	0.94	1.00	0.94	0.74	0.43	0.05	-0.23	-0.35	-0.36
09v	0.21	0.35	0.78	0.94	1.00	0.92	0.67	0.27	-0.10	-0.32	-0.40
10v	0.32	0.48	0.53	0.74	0.92	1.00	0.89	0.57	0.17	-0.14	-0.32
11v	0.48	0.59	0.22	0.43	0.67	0.89	1.00	0.87	0.55	0.20	-0.08
12v	0.56	0.61	-0.06	0.05	0.27	0.57	0.87	1.00	0.88	0.61	0.30
13v	0.51	0.56	-0.24	-0.23	-0.10	0.17	0.55	0.88	1.00	0.90	0.67
14v	0.39	0.45	-0.29	-0.35	-0.32	-0.14	0.20	0.61	0.90	1.00	0.92

15v	0.22	0.23	-0.26	-0.36	-0.40	-0.32	-0.08	0.30	0.67	0.92	1.00
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7 Comparison with ocean models

The eddy kinetic energy have been estimated from the Diadem2 model simulations in the Norwegian Sea (Evensen, 1999) and is shown in Figure 21. The Diadem2 model is based on the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM), originally developed by Rainer Bleck and coworkers at the University of Miami (Bleck et al., 1992). It differs from traditional models by the choice of vertical co-ordinate which is potential density. The use of an orthogonal curvilinear grid allows for the use of a large model domain where high resolution is still retained in the Norwegian Sea area. The model grid is based on a mapping of the poles to two new locations on the earth. The mapping conserves orthogonality for all the grid cells which are all quadratic. The algorithm is presented in (Bentsen et. al., 1999). The Diadem2 model version includes all of the Arctic and has a resolution of approximately 20-25 km along the Gulf Stream extension and down to 10 km in the North Sea. In addition there is a Diadem1 model version with half of this resolution which has been used in this (phase one) project for numerical efficiency.

The eddy kinetic energy from the Diadem2 simulations is not exactly comparable with the EKE from the altimeter data, which has a resolution of $0.2^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$, but should indicate high model variability in the same areas as seen by the altimeter data. The model resolution is too coarse to properly represent the eddy variability in the Nordic Seas. The variability given by Diadem2 indicate similar areas of high variability as the altimeter observations, although it is lower in the model than for the observations. In Figure 21 the variability from a higher resolution (7 km) regional model for the Atlantic Margin is shown. This model is run in a nested mode with the Diadem2 model. Clearly with this resolution the model provides a significantly higher variability which is more in agreement with the observations. We expect that a resolution of less than 4 km is needed in order to properly represent all the mesoscale activity in the Nordic Seas but this is presently not feasible in a sophisticated data assimilation system running on available computers.

Thus, the major result from the comparison between the model and altimeter derived circulation is that both the Diadem1 and the Diadem2 models are too coarse for a direct intercomparison between altimeter and model results. On the other hand, the models and observations provides similar locations for the high and low variability areas, and the large scale structures in the observations seems to match well with the model results.

Figure 21. Eddy kinetic energy averaged over a year from a high resolution (7 km) regional Atlantic Margin model.

8 Conclusion

The study shows that SAR and altimeter data can provide information on mesoscale ocean currents in the Norwegian Sea which is an important supplement to time series of current measurements at single locations, ship measurements, drifting buoys and model simulations.

With SAR images it is possible to map location, size and other geometrical properties of eddies and fronts. Numerous front and eddies are seen in most of the selected images taken during moderate to low wind conditions. The appearance of both feature types was most frequent along the shelf break at the core of the North Atlantic Current. In the comparison made between SAR current features and current measurements reasonable good agreement was found between currents at 100 m depth and the SAR eddy features. The study has shown that eddy patterns appears in nearly 60 % of all the SAR images selected, most frequently from April to August when the wind speed is lower than in the autumn and winter. Thus it is concluded that low-wind SAR images can be used as an operational tool for monitoring of current patterns, mainly in the summer season.

Altimeter data from two satellites (ERS and TOPEX/Poseidon) obtained over a period from 1992 to 1998 were used to calculate seasonal eddy kinetic energy, Reynolds stresses and 10-day averaged geostrophic velocity anomaly fields. Results show clearly the seasonal and geographical variability of both the velocity anomalies and the eddy kinetic energy.

The comparison between altimeter derived current velocity maps and current features seen by SAR indicate that there are mesoscale currents and fronts. Exact comparison is difficult due to the different spatial/temporal properties of the two instruments. In the case of slow-moving or stationary eddies, the current pattern in the SAR image showed good agreement with altimeter derived current velocities. The altimeter velocity fields have not been compared with eddy-resolving models used to simulate the currents in the study area by DNMI, but this could be another interesting study in the future.

In conclusion, satellite SAR and altimeter data have demonstrated that both can play an important role to obtain synoptic information about current regimes over the deepwater areas off the Norwegian coast. Eddy kinetic energy and geostrophic current anomalies can be mapped at regular time intervals on a coarse spatial/temporal scale by the altimeter. SAR images can give a map of current-related features on a much finer spatial scale, but the technique is dependent on low wind conditions.

The study suggests that both SAR and altimeter should be used in monitoring of mesoscale current features as a supplement to traditional current meter moorings.

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